

Designing and implementing citizen-based urban mobility projects: new challenges to the automotive industry in the context of post-pandemic and climate change.

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Abstract: The present study aims to discuss how relations between urban policymakers and citizens are evolving and which effects on the automotive industry are to be expected. Starting from the viewpoint of citizen integration in urban policy decision making, this study draws a categorization of the evolving role of citizens' participation on urban mobility projects and how this is affecting the automotive industry sales and business model strategy. In addition, such discussions consider the time-bound pandemic effects on these stakeholders as well as the role of climate change as a key-factor on driving new urban mobility projects.

Keywords: Urban Mobility; Inclusive Mobility; Mobility-as-a-Service; Citizens' Participation; Automotive Industry.

1. Introduction

With the earliest record of cities tracing back to the Sumer region of Mesopotamia, cities have been around for over 6,000 years (Reba, Reitsma, Karen, & Seto, 2016). For most of this time, city streets were used not only for commuting but also for the dynamics of social, economic, and physical activities that make cities a vital human habitat.

However, as pointed out by (Jones, Marshall, & Boujenko, 2008), over the course of the last century, urban planning and design have been led by traffic engineers who have given priority to the needs of motor vehicles, resulting in urban environments that are unattractive for people on foot, bicycles, and other transport means, whether traveling along the street or using it as a destination for economic or social activities.

For the past hundred years, traffic engineers have been asked the most recurrent question: how many cars can we fit down this street? However, cities and urban planners are starting to raise a different question: how many people can we fit down this street? As quoted by the former mayor of Paris, Bertrand Delanoé: "The fact is that automobiles no longer have a place in the big cities of our time." (Colville-Andersen, 2015).

Thereby, a broader reflection on citizens' relationship with their city and its mobility projects is needed. Among the many actors involved in designing and implementing urban mobility projects, two groups are mainly concerned: urban policymakers and citizens. Globally, the relationships between them follow a top-down approach, firstly between policymakers and mobility providers and later between both these actors and the citizens. Thus, citizen participation is often limited to information campaigns and public consultations.

Conversely, with the widespread adoption of peer-to-peer transport solutions and Mobility-as-a-Service schemes, critical urban mobility decisions are no longer majorly top-down; citizens are starting to reclaim their public urban space, changing their transport modes and commuting patterns consequently the urban environment.

However, with the WHO declaring on yearly 2020 that COVID-19 has become a global pandemic, the relationships between these actors are changing, and the whole urban mobility dynamic. With social distancing and lockdowns, demand for transportation changed dramatically, with steep declines in shared modes – e.g., public transport – and continued increases in individual mobility – e.g., cars and bicycles (Habib & Anik, 2021).

More than two years into the pandemic, society is gradually resuming activities, and demand for transport is returning to pre-pandemic levels. However, this "new normal" requires a reassessment of how mobility projects are conceived and executed, thus impacting the

existing relationships between city governance and its citizens. Thereby, changes in urban mobility posed by the pandemic may not only be an issue but also an opportunity to accelerate and/or create positive change (EIT Urban Mobility, 2021).

Yet, the pandemic can be considered a time-bound crisis, even if quite impacting. The analysis of interactions between citizens and city governance must also integrate two other long-lasting issues: sustainable development and pricing power. These two issues complicate public policies since they often appear contradictory and induce a significant reaction from citizens (as the *gilets jaunes* movement in France after an increase in oil prices or the many pro-climate protests worldwide prompting governments to implement greener measures, e.g., subsidies on EV purchases and city-bans on diesel cars).

This brief description shows that the relationship between citizens and the city government, although quite complex, needs to be renewed. Thereby, this study aims to discuss how relations between urban policymakers and citizens are evolving and which effects on the automotive industry are to be expected.

This paper is composed with 3 sections. Section 2 presents a typology of circumstances that induce policymakers to consider citizens' involvement in the changing patterns of sustainable urban mobility design and execution. Section 3 pictures to which extend citizens empowerment challenges the entire automotive industry and the strategies implemented by companies, car manufacturers and other OEMs, to face these new challenges.

2. Citizen integration in urban policy decision making

2.1. Getting citizens to join a mobility project

(Lindenau & Böhler-Baedeker, 2014) stated that citizens' participation in transport and mobility planning is less studied than participation in other areas of public policy. However, in the last 20 years, there has been a gradual increase in both theory and practice of citizens' participation in mobility planning. The European Commission for instance, has emphasized the relevance of inclusive strategic transport planning, and the development of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP) in several policy documents, such as the Action Plan on Urban Mobility (2009¹), the White Paper Roadmap to a Single European Transport Area (2011)², and the Urban Mobility Package (2013)³.

In fact, in March 2013, the EU approved funding for a four-year project named "CHALLENGE - Addressing Key Challenges of Sustainable Urban Mobility Planning", to provide solutions for the four most pressing challenges in the development, implementation, and assessment of SUMP:

1. **Participation:** actively engaging people and stakeholders in the SUMP process.
2. **Cooperation:** encouraging cooperation among institutional actors.
3. **Measure Selection:** selecting the most effective packages of measures.
4. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** strengthening plan delivery through comprehensive monitoring and evaluation of SUMP measures and processes.

For each of the four proposed challenges, the project has published guidelines⁴ to assist cities and their decision-makers in better addressing such issues in their local communities

¹ Action Plan on urban mobility. Retrieved on February 15th, 2022, from: <https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/clean-transport-urban-transport/urban-mobility/action-plan-urban-mobility_en>.

² White Paper Roadmap to a Single European Transport Area. Retrieved on February 15th, 2022, from: <<https://www.eea.europa.eu/policy-documents/roadmap-to-a-single-european>>.

³ Urban Mobility Package: Retrieved on February 15th, 2022, from: <https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/clean-transport-urban-transport/urban-mobility/urban-mobility-package_en>.

⁴ CHALLENGE project deliverable kits. Retrieved on February 15th, 2022, from: <<http://www.sump-challenges.eu/kits>>.

while designing mobility plans. Hence, getting citizens to join mobility projects entails the issue posed in the first challenge: participation.

Participation reflects the integration of citizens in political planning and decision-making processes and hence the share of power (Lindenau & Böhler-Baedeker, 2014). For the authors, participatory approaches provide a forum to discuss issues, where conflicting views are often expressed, leading to changes and successful outcomes. The benefits of participation, render decision-making more transparent; raise mutual understanding between citizens and public administration; consider ideas, concerns, and everyday knowledge; improve the knowledge basis and have a positive influence on planning processes as it increases acceptability. Therefore, an important reason for citizen participation is to gain knowledge that can inform the preparation of a SUMP (Lindenau & Böhler-Baedeker, 2014).

Several classifications have been developed over the past decades that grade different levels of citizens' participation in government plans. A widely used classification is the ICICE model: Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower (IAP2, 2007). Figure 1 better details the model, describing and exemplifying its five levels.

Figure 1. The ICICE spectrum of public participation
Source: Adapted from IAP2 (2007).

Whether or not these benefits are achieved depends on how the participation process is conducted. If stakeholders and the public are engaged properly, participation can increase the SUMP's quality (Lindenau&Böhler-Baedeker, 2016). Therefore, participation does not automatically lead to an agreement among stakeholders; it is quite the opposite – disagreements need to be accommodated in the decision-making process. Thus, understanding the concept that citizens and policymakers can articulate their ideas and concerns and can contribute with creative and innovative solutions to transport problems, is a fundamental requirement for a sustainable urban mobility plan. The next subsection brings a few examples of successful mobility projects based on citizens' participation.

2.2. Urban Mobility projects

Based on a quick Google search for “citizens’ participation and mobility”, results yielded a wide range of participative actions worldwide. Thus, it was not in our scope to conduct an exhaustive search, but rather to shed light on some projects and actions that show the effectiveness of such participation. Two distinct categories were identified: a) projects without citizens’ participation and b) projects with citizens’ participation.

The former – although not directly within the scope of this study – was included since the outcomes of such projects directly affect local communities (despite not having direct citizens’ participation in their conceptions). Over the next paragraphs, these categories are detailed.

2.2.1. Projects without citizens' participation

A recurring pattern among these projects is the reduction and/or elimination of motor vehicles in certain streets and areas of cities. As (Williams, 2019) explains, although private vehicles revolutionized mobility, they also introduced many ills, from air pollution to traffic accidents. Nonetheless, a growing number of cities are now banning cars from their urban landscape altogether.

(Garfield, 2017) created a list of major cities worldwide that are leading the way toward car-bans. Prior to that, a 2004 European Commission report – “Reclaiming city streets for people: chaos or quality of life?”, listed several cities that have taken actions to redesign streets and neighborhoods toward car-free and human-focused environments. Table 1 depicts some of these examples and their policies and actions. We highlight however that the given examples are non-exhaustive, Wikipedia⁵ maintains a constantly updated list of cities and places worldwide where cars are no longer allowed. To date, the list contains over 60 countries with car-ban projects spread across 268 locations.

Table 1. Global cities and their government-based projects towards car-free environments

City	Action
Madrid (Spain)	Banned old cars from its city center
Paris (France)	First Sunday of every month is car-free
New York (USA)	Banned cars from Central Park
Oslo (Norway)	Banned cars in some streets in the city center
London (England)	Plan to ban cars on half the streets in its city center
Brussels (Belgium)	Fine for old vehicles in its city center
Milan (Italy)	Rolling out a series of bans towards old diesel vehicles
Rome (Italy)	No diesel vehicles by 2024
Bogotá (Colombia)	Car-free streets every Sunday from 7 am to 2 pm.
Kajian (Finland)	Closure of the main square and a section of the main high street to traffic
Strasbourg (France)	Banned cars from the city center
Copenhagen (Denmark)	Development of car-free streets and squares in Copenhagen city center
Nuremberg (Germany)	Traffic bans with the aim of improving air quality
Oxford (England)	Integrated Transport Strategy towards a change in the modal split

Source: Prepared by the authors based on (Garfield, 2017).

At last, it is worth mentioning that such an approach of shifting focus from car-based transport towards a multimodal split may also be applicable not only for the urban commute but also for urban cargo transport. According to the results of the EU-funded project Cycle Logistics (Cialoca, Voinica, & Wrighton, 2019). 51% of all the goods moved around a city could be moved by bikes or other slow-moving last-mile vehicles.

2.2.2. Projects with citizens' participation

Citizens' involvement is one of the fundamental requirements of a SUMP, in a sense that they have local knowledge to provide expertise and opinions which contribute to the development of effective plans and measures (Lindenau & Böhler-Baedeker, 2014). Such involvement encourages both citizens and policymakers to take ownership of sustainable mobility ideas, transport policies, and projects. Similar to the examples in section 2.2.1., we highlight some results of three major European projects: the CIVITAS ELAN project, the aforementioned CH4ALLENGE project, and the CITIZEN project.

Launched by the EU in 2002 the CIVITAS program consisted of a network of cities dedicated to cleaner, better transport in Europe and beyond. With the approach of “putting the citizen first” in 2012, the program published a report named: “CIVITAS ELAN: Work and Lessons Learned Related to Citizen Engagement” (Marega, et al., 2012) in which the cities of

⁵ List of car-free places. Retrieved from: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_car-free_places> on April 21th, 2022.

Ljubljana (Slovenia), Gent (Belgium), Zagreb (Croatia), Brno (Czech Republic) and Porto (Portugal) joined on the mission to mobilize their citizens by developing mobility solutions for their cities, ensuring health and access for all. The report brings results from these cities with several study cases of citizens' participation in the three main stages of a mobility project: plan; implementation and evaluation.

The CHALLENGE project surveyed 34 cities from across Europe and beyond about their transport planning practices and the status of their current transport plans and Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP).

At last, the CitiZEN project lead by Energy Cities⁶, was a consortium with six of their member cities – Bistrița (Romania), Čačak (Serbia), Milton-Keynes (United Kingdom), Modena (Italy), Växjö (Sweden) and Zadar (Croatia) – from 2015 to 2017 with the purpose of tackling the development and update of local Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans by the cities local authorities as well as implementation of specific actions, such as: promotion of cycling, car sharing, sustainable mobility in schools (walking buses, awareness campaigns), family contests, public events (e.g. energy days/fairs, European mobility week) allowing citizens to learn about local, national and European experiences in terms of products and services related to sustainable mobility.

Table 2 summarizes some of the main results found in these projects considering citizens' participation in urban mobility projects.

Table 2. Examples of projects with citizens' participation

City	Gent (Belgium)
Project's goal	Re-develop the main train station area.
Citizen's participation (ICICE levels)	<i>Inform:</i> information “markets” & guided tours. <i>Consult:</i> Facebook questionnaire. <i>Involve:</i> 9 group meetings, 35 “reduced discomfort” meetings, and dialogue cafes.
Main outcomes	Closure of a street for all motorized traffic. Decision to not open a new tunnel in the neighborhood.
City	Porto (Portugal)
Project's goal	Implement a new Demand Responsive Transport (DRT) service in the city.
Citizen's participation (ICICE levels)	<i>Inform:</i> dissemination campaign to raise awareness among potential users. <i>Consult:</i> surveys to measure users' satisfaction with the service. <i>Involve:</i> survey among users (university students) to define the service's route, working days and time. <i>Collaborate:</i> partnership between the public transport operator with a sponsor and local shops to provide additional benefits to users.
Main outcomes	Definition of the DRT service route and timetable. 19-week demonstration service providing a new commute option for students travelling between the city center and the university quarter.
City	Brno (Czech Republic)
Project's goal	Provide better public transport service for people with disabilities (especially those using wheelchairs).
Citizen's participation (ICICE levels)	<i>Involve:</i> discussion groups with disabled people to discuss whether the service should remain operating on regular routes or if it should become a DRT. <i>Collaborate:</i> workshops and discussion groups with disabled people to design the technical specifications for the new minibuses.
Main outcomes	Document with the technical specifications for the tender for the new minibuses. Decision to keep the buses as a regular fixed line service.
City	Ljubljana (Slovenia)
Project's goal	Implement a DRT service for people with disabilities

⁶ Energy Cities is the European Association of local authorities in energy transition. It represents 1000 towns and cities in 30 European countries. Link: <<http://www.energy-cities.eu/>> Accessed on 18/05/2022.

Citizen's participation (ICICE levels)	<i>Involve</i> : several focus groups with the target audience to help properly design the service and to train the bus drivers to cope with the users' special needs.
Main outcomes	The operator has given a lot of attention to educating and training the drivers (to give special attention the passengers as well as aid and inform when needed). The service is now operating successfully, and satisfied customers are raising awareness and acceptance of new transport opportunity.
City	Amiens (France)
Project's goal	Renew the city's SUMP
Citizen's participation (ICICE levels)	<i>Involve</i> : citizen-based workshops to gain in-depth insights and opinions. <i>Collaborate</i> : formulation of a collective SUMP action plan.
Main outcomes	Measures proposed by the group of citizens were considered and labelled in the final SUMP proposal.
City	Budapest (Hungary)
Project's goal	Gather local insights for the city's SUMP reformulation
Citizen's participation (ICICE levels)	<i>Inform</i> : creation of a dedicated website (presenting the SUMP and related information). <i>Consult</i> : online questionnaire to survey the importance of the SUMP's objectives. <i>Involve</i> : series of stakeholder forum, and opportunities to submit written comments (online, via email and letters). <i>Collaborate</i> : invitation of foreign partners and experts to review the draft SUMP.
Main outcomes	This mixed-method approach marked a turning point in the city's planning practices towards wide and meaningful citizens' participation
City	Modena (Italy)
Project's goal	Promote walking for short distance urban trips (within a 10km ² radius) using a "transit-like" map indicating the walking distance between desired points.
Citizen's participation (ICICE levels)	<i>Inform</i> : communication campaign, to encourage walking trips. <i>Consult</i> : active feedback from citizens and requests to expand the project for cycling.
City	Växjö (Sweden)
Project's goal	Promote cycling as the ultimate means of transport for the urban commute.
Citizen's participation (ICICE levels)	<i>Inform</i> : creation of a logo (for social network photo profiles), and a certification label (for businesses/workplaces). <i>Involve</i> : get the citizens to add the logo and the label to their profile pictures on their social networks to help raise awareness and encourage the population towards more eco-friendly modes of transport. <i>Collaborate</i> : the profile picture was created in collaboration with the city bicycle dealers, associations, and the municipality.

Source: Prepared by the authors based on (Marega, et al., 2012), (IAP2, 2007), and (Energy Cities, 2017)).

2.3. Schematic model

Considering the examples given in the previous sections, we propose a schema to synthesize and overview the ways in which urban mobility projects are implemented. As previously discussed, urban mobility projects and plans are mainly implemented via one of the two categories: government-based actions without, and with citizens' participation.

The projects that fall into the first category (without citizens' participation) are anchored at the left-end side of the model presented in Figure 2 and, have as their main feature a top-down approach. As stated by (Biosca, 2017), traditional planning methodologies are strongly based on top-down approaches, in which plans are made a priori and only after citizens are informed about them. According to the author, plans made without citizen involvement often do not reflect the problems faced by people, and consequently, citizens naturally tend to feel a lower degree of ownership and responsibility for maintaining the final public infrastructure.

Figure 2. Schematic model of urban mobility projects implementation
Source: Prepared by the authors.

On the other end of this spectrum, some measures and changes within urban mobility need quick and effective responses that in some cases, cannot be fully delivered by government actions (even in projects with citizen's participation). In this sense, some communities and citizen groups are taking matters into their own hands and are taking the approach of "acting prior to asking". Due to their bottom-up and "informal" nature, examples belonging to this category are rather scattered and not formally structured. Good examples that fit this category of projects are given by the architect and urban designer Mikael Colville-Andersen on his television documentary "The Life-Sized City" (TVOntario, 2017), where over the three seasons of the show, he visited various world cities (e.g. Medellín, Paris, Bangkok, Tel Aviv, Cape Town, Detroit, Montreal, Taipei, Buenos Aires, New Orleans, among others), where it profiles innovative local urban development and improvement projects that are changing and revitalizing city life.

At last, the projects with citizens' participation are in the middle of the spectrum. In these types of projects, measures can have citizen participation in the planning, implementation, and evaluation stages. It should be noted that citizens' participation can occur in several different ways, thus it is up to the project managers to choose the:

- **Desired participation:** based, for instance, on the classification model presented in Figure 1.
- **Data collection and interaction:** focus groups, interviews, surveys, etc. It should be noted here that triangulation of methods, if well applied, can be an interesting tool for data collection - as seen in the example of Budapest for their SUMP development.
- **Interaction environment:** as seen in the examples, several projects opted for face-to-face interaction with citizens while others used the virtual environment for collaboration and in some cases, a combined approach was also used.

It is worth noting that with the widespread adoption and popularization of internet-connected devices, the use of online tools and applications have grown exponentially. As exemplified by (Kintziger, 2017), the European startup Citizen Lab, created an online platform whose goal is to facilitate citizen participation. Through the platform, cities can inform their citizens about upcoming projects, gather feedback, and make more oriented decisions. Hoplr, another European start-up, aims to create online communities where neighbors can discuss neighborhood-related topics. Cities and citizens can use this knowledge to better understand what it really means to "live" in the community and act accordingly.

Over the next section, we detail the impacts of this citizen-oriented urban mobility approach on the automotive industry, aiming to show the importance of considering citizens' options not only at the urban policy plan, but also at the strategic decisions of OEMs, once their products (cars, motorcycles, buses, etc.) are among the key components of the urban transport system.

3. Impacts of a citizen-centric mobility on the automotive industry

As presented in Section 2, policy makers are increasingly adopting a citizen-centric view in their urban planning. For that purpose, they do not necessarily need to implement a full bottom-up approach (Figure 2). Indeed, public transport is very often characterized by multilevel government which allows a better fit to local needs. The existence of a local integrator policy organization at level implementing local mobility policy has a direct impact on operation efficiency and citizens' orientation. In this multilayer's decision process, the city government can fully delegate operations to the integrator and concentrate on citizen needs expression, anticipation, and innovation deployment. The challenge is to integrate citizens, to optimize communication throughout these layers to create value for the city and its citizens (Mira-Bonnardel & Couzineau, 2021)

In consonance with our schematic model from Figure 2, (Cohendet, Grandadam, & Laurent, 2010) depicted and analyzed the dynamics of the creative city by defining three different layers – the *upper ground*, the *middle ground* and the *underground* – as the basic components of the creative processes in local innovative milieus. Each one of these layers intervenes with specific characteristics in the creative process and enables new knowledge to transit from an informal micro-level to a formal macro-level.

- The *upper ground* concerns all institutional public and private actors who operate through market or redistributive mechanisms.
- The *underground* brings together individual or collective non-market actors (associations, citizens' collectives) who contribute to the creative bubbling at the origin of new ideas. Unlike the *upper ground*, market and redistributive mechanisms are absent from the *underground*, in favor of economic mechanisms based on reciprocity. The activities carried out in the *underground* are therefore freed from the constraints of economic valorization and benefit from greater latitude for experimentation.
- The *middle ground* aggregates creative ideas from the *underground*. It forms a space for the circulation of creative ideas developed as part of underground exploration activities with a view to their valorization by the commercial and redistributive mechanisms within the *upper ground*. Four *middle ground* elements can be distinguished: places and platforms, activated by events and projects.

During the whole twentieth century, urban mobility was strongly driven by the upper ground imposing a top-down process for urban mobility shaping; actors of the upper ground were policy makers largely influenced by lobbying actions from car manufacturers and other important OEMs. The twenty-first century has opened opportunities for the middle ground with newcomers boosted by the Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) paradigm, like carsharing companies BlaBlaCar, Liftshare or Car2Go. Carsharing generated almost 100 million US\$ for more than 680 million users in 2021 (Statista, 2022). New mobility models have emerged in this rebalancing of powers, anchoring the fourfold product-service-structure-market into a safer and more sustainable economy.

3.1 Citizens mobility expectation a threat on the automotive industry?

This empowerment of the underground is strengthened by 1) public policy makers giving more attention to citizens' opinion, and 2) the middle ground dynamic leveraged by the MaaS paradigm.

Regarding urban mobility, citizen are demanding actions on four levels: they ask public policy makers to reduce pollution by CO₂ emissions, increase road safety, decrease congestion in cities, and lower noise pollution (Tsavachidis & Le Petit, 2022). To meet these challenges, local governments need to reshape their urban transport system. For that purpose, city policy

makers use various measures, such as regulations and taxation, investments in infrastructure and equipment.

Representing more than a quarter of the world's greenhouse gas emissions, transport plays a key role in fighting against climate change. At the U.N. World Conference on Sustainable Transport, the Secretary António Guterres called on governments to encourage clean transport options and invest in sustainable and resilient transport systems. “Public transport should be the foundation of urban mobility. For every dollar invested, it creates three times more jobs than building new highways”, he said. For Mr. Guterres, “the next nine years must be marked by a global transition to renewable energy, and sustainable transport is at the heart of this transformation”.

As a result of this shift to sustainable mobility solutions, up to one out of ten new cars sold in 2030 may likely be a shared vehicle, which could reduce sales of private-use vehicles. This would mean that more than 30 percent of miles driven in new cars sold could be from shared mobility. On this trajectory, one out of three new cars sold could potentially be a shared vehicle as soon as 2050 (Gao, Kaas, Mohr, & Wee, 2016).

Some examples illustrate how local governments have implemented mobility policies to meet citizens' expectations. Some cities, like Copenhagen in Denmark or Lille in France, have organized "car-free neighborhoods", giving rise to the development of sustainable neighborhoods, creating a harmonious cohabitation between the different transport modes and, consequently minimizing the place given to cars in the public arena, either in parking or road space.

In the country of Luxembourg as well as in the city Dunkerque (France), urban transport is entirely free of charge for its inhabitants. For the mayor of Dunkerque, this choice of a free urban transport service is linked to social and climate issues. Free public transport encourages urban citizen to adopt a sustainable behavior and meanwhile it increases their pricing power. Consequently, in Dunkerque the number of cars on the road decreased and travels by public transport increased by 85% from 2015 to 2020 according to the Observatory of Cities of Free Transport. A study conducted by researchers from the VIGS association (Innovative Cities and Knowledge Management) shows that 48% of public transport new users parted with their car.

In 2020, Luxembourg became the first country in the world to make public transport free of charge throughout its territory. And this measure applies to residents as well as to tourists and cross-border commuters from France, Belgium, or Germany. This decision is part of Luxembourg government's mobility strategy for 2025 which aims to change the way citizens are commuting. Thus, the country's government encourages travelers to use bicycles and public transport. As pointed out by (Strang, 2022), according to a survey conducted one year after the free fares were introduced, there was a 65% increase in use during weekdays, and a 125% increase on weekends. Half of those surveyed said their public transport use had increased since it was made free, half of which had ditched their car for public transport.

Although the devastating effects of the Covid19 pandemic on the middle ground dynamics, the stakeholders in this sector are quickly bouncing back, and Innovation on Mobility Services (IMS) are booming, drastically transforming urban mobility. IMS include carsharing, ride hailing, bike sharing, ridesharing, micro transit, and scooter sharing programs, and collectively these are opening new branches or expanding in cities across the globe (Shaheen & Cohen, 2020). Ride hailing services provided by companies such as Uber and Lyft have grown rapidly. Almost ten years after the creation of the first Transportation Network Company (TNC), ride hailing is now available in more than 300 U.S. cities, and one in four people in major U.S. metropolitan areas has used this type of mobility option (Clewlow & Mishra, 2017).

Still concerning the middle ground, the pandemic boosted bicycle services. A study conducted by the French association (ADEME, 2021) focuses on 7 types of bicycle services: secure parking, short and long-term bike-sharing solutions, subsidies for bike purchase, self-

repair workshops, workplace services, and a focus on cycling schools taking part in the “know how to ride” program. According to this study, in France bicycle pooling grew by 86% in 2020, with 162 companies offering this service and 120.000 rented bicycles. Thereby, bicycle services have an influence on the motorization rate: 13% of the bike renters claim that bicycle services push them to part with their car and 12% to give up buying a car; besides, the survey measured that 12% of bicycle users have become regular public transport users.

The examples we put forward in this section show that when policy makers consider citizen expectations, or even empower citizens, the implemented measures tend to reduce the need for a car purchase, these measures induce citizens to switch from car’s possession to car’s use. In that sense, empowering citizen threaten the whole car industry and more specifically car manufacturers.

3.2 The automotive industry adaptation

With all these projects and trends, as well as the initial and aftershocks from the pandemic, the automotive industry is probably facing the biggest disruption of its history. Companies need to find an effective balance between economic sustainability, environmental regulations, and citizens satisfaction (Canitez, 2019). To properly play the game, the companies are urged to redefine their product range to offer a combined product-service system (PSS) and even a modular product-service system (MPSS). As a result, traditional players from the *upper ground*, mainly car manufacturers and other OEMs are obliged to redesign their offer and value proposition to clients with technological innovations and customized services. The automotive companies have been proposing mainly three answers: shared mobility, vehicle electrification and vehicle automation (Miskolczi, Földes, Munkacsy, & Jaszberenyi, 2021)

To rapidly develop their product and service portfolio within this new framework, car manufacturers chose to sign new strategic alliances with “non-traditional” stakeholders in the industry (such as IT companies; startups; telecoms, etc.). Partnership strategy is a recurrent choice in the automotive industry (Attias & Mira-Bonnardel, 2017). For the las decade, alliances expanded the automotive ecosystem with newcomers either companies operating result-oriented services or automated cars manufacturers, both capturing an important part of the opportunities offered by MaaS.

A study by (Ramirez-Portilla, Brown, & Cagno, 2014) on the world’s ten biggest automobile manufacturers shows that these companies have all considerably boosted their open innovation practices since 2005, developing multiple partnerships. Firstly, by forging vertical connections between customers and suppliers that are particularly prolific innovators in the car sector, where parts manufacturers have for a long time been partners with high innovation capacity; then bolstering these alliances with horizontal connections with competitors; lastly, by extending the partnership scope to take in complementary companies in the IoT industry (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Major Automakers' Partnerships Related to Mobility, Connectivity, and Driving Automation
 Source: Center for automotive research (2021).

The combination of shared mobility with vehicle electrification has opened the way for vehicle automation. In that regard, the biggest watershed in Autonomous Vehicle (AVs) research and development happened in 2004/2005 in the United States with a series of annual public challenges, called DARPA Grand Challenges (Gandia, et al., 2018) from which countless contributions and advances have been made in vehicle automation, bringing the indoors-laboratory research to the streets, and shifting the focus to beyond technological aspects.

Therefore, AVs are today a prominent alternative to urban mobility needs, facilitating driving; increasing road safety; reducing emissions and traffic jams; as well as allowing drivers to choose to do different things other than driving. Thus, access to fully automated vehicles would also improve mobility for those who cannot, or do not want to drive (Schellekens, 2015). Thereby, automation has a great potential to improve urban mobility while opening the doors to a more adapted, flexible, inclusive, on-demand collective transportation, thus offering a solution for larger cities that struggle to provide adequate public transport to support their citizens' needs.

In fact, public urban road transport is already ahead of the curve when it comes to automation. Besides the well-advanced tests by Google's subsidiary Waymo (with their 5-seater automated vehicles), within the scope of current deployments, the most widely tested upper-automation level vehicles (SAE's levels 3 and 4) are Autonomous Vehicles for Collective Transport (AVCTs) (Antoniali, 2021).

AVCTs are electric automated vehicles equipped with a wide-range of sensors and cameras that today can carry from 5 to 12 passengers with the main goal of fulfilling the first- and last-mile parts of the commute, as well as micro transit for city centers, central business districts, university campuses, airports, shopping malls, hospitals, etc. By being in the higher automation levels, such vehicles do not require the constant monitoring and intervention of a human operator, which allows transport operators greater flexibility in their business models offerings in terms of working hours of their vehicles, routes (fixed or on-demand), and even target audience (commuters, tourists, cargo, etc) (Antoniali, 2021)

On a prospective study carried out by (Miskolczi, Földes, Munkacsy, & Jaszberenyi, 2021), the authors worked on urban mobility scenarios for 2030s. They defined 52 scenarios outlining the possible future state of mobility and reached the conclusion that: "the spread of shared mobility solutions, electrification, and automation of vehicles are the technological solutions

that shape the future of urban mobility. Scenario analysis proved that key themes are shared mobility and automation” (Miskolczi, Földes, Munkacsy, & Jaszberenyi, 2021).

In this sense, one may raise the following question: Are the companies from the automotive industry prepared for this scenario? Carmakers are accelerating the electrification of their production, but the transition is proving complex, with several issues being raised about the financing aspects, the impact on jobs, and the implementation of changes (varied degrees of opposition from customers, governments, and the industry itself). Thus, regarding vehicle electrification, the revolution is starting with newcomers and startups disrupting the automotive industry by introducing innovating technologies at lightning speed, reducing battery prices, and opening the possibility of commercializing electric vehicles with mass-market appeal. Among these startups we find in France for example: Batteries for People (optimization of electric consumption), Transition-One (transformation of fuel car into an electric car), WattPark (shard charging station), Greenmove (electric car renting), Dreev (V2G, vehicle to grid solution), Clem (electric car sharing with its e-MaaS platform – electro Mobility as a Service).

Concerning automation, traditional car manufacturers are not making the headlines in terms of R&D, most of the innovation is currently coming from newcomers (such as Tesla) and tech giants (Google-Waymo). Yet, AVs will offer high value to consumer and an increasing sales outlet for companies, as shown in Figure 4. Once more the change is being driven by startups, among which the following 25 companies are ushering in the next generation of travel: Motional, Uber, AutoX, Optimus Ride, Arity, WiTricity, Unity Technologies, Ouster, Cruise, Waymo, Voyage, Swift Navigation, Embark Truck, CARMERA, Zoox, Nauto.

Figure 4. New-vehicle market share of Avs in 2030
 Source: Mac Kinsey, 2016

This brief description of the main challenges the automotive industry must cope with shows that the secular automotive ecosystem is about to experience important changes. The shift to an urban mobility ecosystem centered on citizens is creating a new innovation momentum, impacting the entire automobile industry and moving the boundaries of value creation and value sharing.

Automobile manufacturers, constrained and pressured to be constantly agile, must reinvent their strategy for a new century of development led by innovation and aiming at sustainable, responsible mobility. As cars are increasingly integrated into the connected world, automakers will have no choice but to participate in the new mobility ecosystem that is emerging because of citizens empowerment. To keep their standard as upper ground actors, OEMs need to align their skills and processes to address new challenges like software-enabled consumer value definition, cybersecurity, data privacy, and continuous product-service updates.

4. Concluding remarks

In this post-pandemic period, modes of travel, work and lifestyle are being called into question. The mobility offer has effectively been forced to adapt, even more so as ecological awareness is being raised by governments, mobility stakeholders and citizens.

Therefore, the need for fast, ecological, comfortable, and inexpensive solutions is a challenge for all mobility stakeholders: public and private operators, manufacturers, local authorities and users. But, is the involvement of citizens in the decision to implement new mobility solutions effective? Will the changes in behavior linked to eco-responsible solutions be sustainable?

For the automotive industry, the challenges are considerable if we consider all these factors such as new technologies, energy choices (hydrogen versus lithium electric battery), recycling channels and the hyper-competitiveness of the automotive markets. The future of the automobile will have to deal with this new post-pandemic mode of relationship where in cities, a reconfiguration of urban space is at work through new mobility solutions (bicycle lanes, pedestrian spaces) and through a desire to involve citizen-users in the public debate.

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